

INNOVATIVE ASPECTS OF RESEARCH OF VENTURE INVESTING IN THE USA

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The US economy is characterized by a significant influence of the venture industry, which is developing at a significant pace, which determines the relevance of this research topic. Ammosov Yu.P., Bagiev G.L., Gulkina P.G., Dagaev A.A., Karzanova I.V., Kashirin A.I., Kotelnikova V.Yu., Nikkonen A.I., Revazova V.G., Semenova A.S. and other authors. However, some aspects were not fully considered, which indicates the need for further research.

The purpose of this work is to study the innovative aspects of venture capital investment in the United States. The tasks are as follows:

- 1) to define the concept of "venture investment", to identify the fundamental differences between the main models of venture investment in the United States;
- 2) analyze the trends in the development of venture capital investment in the USA;
- 3) determine the role of venture capital investment in the US economy.

Venture investment is a long-term, risky capital invested in the shares of new and rapidly growing companies in order to obtain high profits after the shares of these companies are listed on the stock exchange [2].

In the United States, venture capital investment is the most developed in the world and is presented in the form of various models and organizational forms, the key difference between which is the goals of venture investors: investments of venture capital firms are carried out with the aim of obtaining a high level of investment income; investments of individuals (business angels) and their associations - in order to obtain a high level of investment income, as well as from the desire to engage in entrepreneurial activities and for personal reasons; venture investments of non-financial corporations - in order to obtain new technologies, diversify or support companies, as well as to obtain a high level of investment income; venture investments of commercial and investment banks - in order to obtain a high level of return on invested capital, as well as to obtain a synergistic effect with the main activities of banks; venture investments with the participation of the state - with the aim of developing small

business and knowledge-intensive sectors of the country's economy, solving social problems, etc. [1].

The fundamental differences between the organizational forms and models of venture investment lie not only in the different goals of venture investors, but also in their use of various organizational and legal forms of doing business, as well as specific decision-making and investment management mechanisms, and varying degrees of responsibility for investment results.

Venture capital is important to the US economy because venture capital stimulates innovation, which is the basis of the American economic model, and supports high-growth companies that eventually become an essential part of the US economy. The impact of venture capital on the US economy is characterized by the following aspects: venture capital supports fast-growing companies that eventually become an essential part of the country's economy; venture capital stimulates innovation, which is the basis of the modern American economy [3].

The role of venture capital-backed companies in the US economy is very significant because they are more dynamic than other firms.

Venture capital is an important element of the US national innovation system. This is due to the fact that it is aimed at supporting small, fast-growing companies, usually operating in high-tech sectors of the American economy or using innovative business models.

Thus, venture investment is essential for the innovative development of the United States; venture capital is aimed at supporting small fast-growing companies; in the high-tech industries of the American economy, there is a tendency to further decline.

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